

Quality 5.0: Leveraging user-centric value based Quality 4.0

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Abstract. Currently, cybersecurity and privacy have been considered some of its important challenges. This research aims to develop methodologies/techniques to enhance the existing Quality 4.0 principles into the new concept of Quality 5.0 through human-centricity. It will include new concepts of requirements elicitation, quality measurement and assurance, efficiency, and human satisfaction. This thesis will also promote a reference architecture for conceived Quality 5.0 lifecycle and a selection of tools for implementing it inside Industry 5.0.

Keywords: Industry 5.0 · human-centric · Quality 4.0 · Quality 5.0

1 Introduction

IoT (Internet of Things) and Industry 4.0 continuously provide opportunities and challenges in different domains and contexts, especially for better and more productive autonomous systems. However, the growth of their hardware and software complexity opens the way to new and more critical security and privacy threats and violations that may raise severe consequences for financial loss and society's trustworthiness [11]. Additionally, pressure from time to market often forces industries and developers towards massive use of available third-party or open-source components that could increase the cybersecurity risks if not adequately tested. Finally, if, from one side, the commonly adopted cloud solutions and data analytics (like, Google Cloud, Microsoft Azure, and Amazon [2] improve the IOT integrability [1], the other still requires robust trustable and reliable solutions and components. Indeed, digitalization and automation brought various business benefits. Still, modern industrial systems require more efficient, trusted, and secure ways of communication, innovative and smart architectures, and precise business models and processes [3, 7]. To better manage the quality of the IoT systems and provide measurable evidence, in early 2015, the concept of Quality 4.0 was introduced [13]. This leverages traditional guidelines and technologies for quality management, deeply relying on emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and data analytics. Some fundamental principles of Quality 4.0 include a customer-centric approach, data-driven decision-making to collect and analyze quality data, continuous improvement, like real-time monitoring

and predictive analytics, and agility and flexibility properties for quick changes and recovery management. However, despite the positive impact of Quality 4.0 in delivering high-quality services and products, there is still no consensus and adequate understanding of how to use it inside the Industry 5.0 context [15]. This is the next generation of the industrial development process focused on integrating advanced digital technologies with human capabilities. Indeed, Quality 4.0 represents an essential improvement for Industry 5.0 [27], but there are still several challenges to be addressed, such as:

CH1: Adopting human-centric development. The collaboration between human workers and advanced digital technologies should be improved during the development activities because it could impact the overall quality. Indeed the interaction between people and machines may impact security, safety, accessibility, privacy, trust, and other quality attributes in different ways.

CH2: Usage of innovative technologies. The new highly personalized software, systems, and products should be properly tested and validated to guarantee the overall quality level and the avoidance of threats of failures.

CH3: Integrating Cybersecurity and Privacy. The rapid integration process and the use of advanced digital technologies can create vulnerability of cybersecurity threats that may impact the integrity, accountability, and privacy-preserving of the data and its products.

CH4: Leveraging automation. Use of automatic tools and facilities for verification and validation activities and for guaranteeing the required quality level has a key role in reducing the cost and risk of the industry 5.0.

CH5: Increasing the by-design regulatory compliance. To reduce the maintenance cost and the expense of in-production failure repair, the integration and use of the different advanced digital technologies in manufacturing processes, organizations need to be by-design compliant with new regulatory requirements related to quality control and data security.

2 Outline of Objectives

Focusing on the five challenges described in the previous section, the main objective of this proposal is to:

OB1: define the Quality 5.0 concepts. i.e., leverage Quality 4.0 in Industry 5.0 by proposing a new Quality 5.0 concept focused on promoting a human-centric development and quality assessment process. It will include new concepts of requirements elicitation, quality measurement and assurance, efficiency, and human satisfaction.

OB2: provide a Quality 5.0 reference lifecycle. i.e., by-design define the activities and phases useful for assuring and assessing the Quality 5.0 along all the development process steps.

OB3: provide a reference architecture. i.e., provide a reference architecture for conceived lifecycle and a selection of tools for implementing Quality 5.0 inside Industry 5.0.

3 State of the art

Quality 4.0 emphasizes traditional methodologies or techniques for quality management. The main goal of Quality 4.0 is to enhance the quality and implementation of Industry 4.0 and further move into Industry 5.0. Quality 4.0 is a relatively new concept in the market, and it requires a lot of unification to be categorized as a good technique to improve Industry 4.0 and modern-day cybersecurity challenges. Therefore, we must broaden the scope of Quality 4.0 while utilizing modern-day quality assurance and testing techniques to improve cybersecurity. Quality will always be one of the most important dimensions of services and products to be adopted in worldwide markets [5]. Software companies or multinationals can achieve a competitive advantage by effectively implementing quality to compete with market rivals by reevaluating industries' role and their impact on 4.0 manages quality in the modern era of Industry 4.0 [24, 25, 23]. As anticipated in the introduction, the major challenges for implementing Quality 4.0 in organizations are: i) The authenticity of data; ii) The role of big data in driving quality programs; iii) Improved customer satisfaction; iv) Cost-effective and better resource utilization. However, in promoting the positive relationship between technology and humans and the goal-oriented methods used to meet the quality objectives and improve the organization's strategy as highlighted in [4] some issues still need to be solved, such as: i) The unclear return on investment and high implementation costs; ii) Lack of resources and implementation knowledge; iii) Poor organizational culture; iv) Lack of understanding of competitive advantage.

Fig. 1. Evolution Process.

As shown in Figure 1, the solution of this proposal will try to solve them by proposing a new concept of quality: Quality 5.0. As in the Figure, Industry 4.0 has been largely techno-economic rather than socio-economic; consequently, cybersecurity and privacy have been considered as important challenges. Industry 4.0's main weakness relies on managing interaction because it has given access to cyber-attackers. Today, as evidenced by the many industrial examples and literature and the many focused call-for-proposals at the European level, one of the most effective means for preventing main criticalities and breaches is to promote the by-design adoption of Cybersecurity from a broader perspective [9, 10] (from the specification to implementation and testing activities). Consider-

ing instead, Industry 5.0, the seminal concept was proposed by Michael Rada in 2015 [6] on social media. After some preliminary research, it was legitimized by the European Commission in January 2021 during the definition of European Union goals for 2030 [6, 12, 20, 27]. Indeed, the main focus of the European Commission document is to promote digital transformation and innovation in organizations and companies to make them more human-centric and sustainable [8, 14]. In particular, the ideology of Industry 5.0 is aligned with European societal objectives and Society 5.0, such as resilient development, employment opportunities, industrial sustainability, needs, and ecosystem limitations [18]. The new Quality 5.0 principles presented in this proposal provide solutions in several directions. 1) They want to improve industrial workers' well-being and develop a human-centric approach [14]. 2) In line with the three core pillars of Industry 5.0 (sustainability, resilience and human centricity [16] the proposed Quality 5.0 principles want to leverage human values and integrate them into innovative digital technologies. As shown in Figure 1, the proposed Quality 5.0 principles want to contribute to the transition from Industry 4.0 to 5.0. They focus on quality management and assessing the relationship between users/humans and intelligent systems [17]. Quality 4.0 measures processes and technologies to improve accuracy and optimize industrial processes. It 5.0 focuses on the human factors, intentions and desires during their synergy and collaboration with machines [18, 22]. Additionally, among the different properties, this proposal will dedicate specific attention to **Human-Centric Cybersecurity and How to make "People Matter"**. Various organizations and companies still neglect the "human risk factor" in their organizational policies or implement outdated or assent driven 'tick-the-box' techniques to train their employees about modern-day cyber security [26] (Professor Phil Morgan, Director of the Human Factors Excellence Research Group at Cardiff University). Research from Stanford University [26] revealed that 88% of security breaches occurred because of human negligence or error. During the Covid-19 phase and later in 2021, the companies became victims of ransomware attacks every eleven seconds. Another study [26] also shows that 96% of data breaches originated through a phishing Email. In ensuring cyber-security, we must focus on socio-technical cybersecurity or human-centric approaches. Humans are a major component or point of focus in this approach.

4 Methodology and Expected outcomes

This proposal will analyze recent approaches, methods, and tools able to target the challenges presented in the introduction. As schematized in Figure 1 this proposal wants to provide a solution to shift from productivity to quality and enhance the organisation's quality management through advanced smart automation and technology. Then, targeting the first objective presented in Section 2, the term "Quality 5.0" will be defined, and its guidelines aligned for their use in "Industry 5.0." context. Quality 5.0 will be therefore conceived in parallel with the management of Industry 5.0 quality. It also will focus on the well-being of

all living beings, analyse the impact of the services produced for Society 5.0 and the manufacturing processes and evaluate energy-efficient production practices, carbon emissions and the impact on the green economy. The pillars of the solution of this proposal will be the definition of a people-first and human-centric approach to cybersecurity and privacy that can convert users and employees into proactive warriors. The intention is to provide means and facilities to let people understand cybersecurity and privacy risks, guide their behaviours, and let them control and manage the desired quality level. According to the second and third objectives of section 2, a Quality 5.0 reference lifecycle and its reference architecture will be developed to promote a human-centric approach for organisations, industries, and companies able to connect human behaviour to engineering and attributes of computer science and to formalise a holistic methodology for cyber-risk management.

As schematised in Figure 5(a) proposal will also focus on the impact of human factors on the use of tools, methods, and theories and the merging of psychology, engineering, and other traditional disciplines. The objective is to improve the relationship or understanding between people and the technology they are utilising and reduce the communication gap that leads to cyber-attacks' success. Therefore, a better industrial transformation and quality largely cannot be separated from a human-centric approach; future initiatives must address human and Societal priorities and security issues.

The following research questions will be considered to target the objectives in Section 2. **1)** Are the available Quality 4.0 techniques enough to enhance cybersecurity? **2)** Are the adopted solutions human-centric? **3)** To what extent can the new Quality 5.0 concepts and architecture improve cybersecurity testing? **4)** To what extent can the by-design Human-Centric approach improve the trustworthiness of the user/consumer?

5 Stage of Research, Past Work and Preliminary Results

The research began in November 2022, and is currently in the middle of the first (over 3) year of a PhD program. The research activity will finish in November 2025. The current proposal has been conceived leveraging the work done in the previous master's thesis [29]. This preliminary proposal focused on requirements traceability as effective means for improving the elicitation process and enhancing the system's quality. The thesis has demonstrated how the requirements traceability process helps and protects against software defects, ensures that the product meets the user's requirements initially documented for the development and decreases the number of bugs in a product with an increase in the overall quality. In this proposal, we leverage the concept of traditional traceability to *Human-Centric Traceability* (HCT): requirements elicitation must involve different sources of knowledge: human needs and values, regulations, standards, functional and non-functional needs and quality level. Thus, traceability pieces of evidence and results should be externalized to all stakeholders involved in the human-centric development process. HCT will be included in the methodologies

Fig. 2. (a) Quality 5.0 Reference Lifecycle. (b) Human-Centric Traceability (HCT).

used in this proposal to enhance Quality 4.0 to Quality 5.0. In Figure 5(b), the new HCT and the connection with the future research activity of this proposal are schematised. In particular, the HCT will involve the following actors: **A1 Human/Users** that are the ultimate targets to achieve better requirements elicitation and ultimately Quality 4.0. **A2 Business Analyst:** who focuses on business aspects that can be optimized. They work collaboratively with other users or stakeholders throughout the business hierarchy to render changes. **A3 Developers:** whose primary role is to build or develop products, software and systems according to human-centric collected requirements to achieve quality and improve global trustworthiness. Therefore, the developers must manage requirements from users, business analysts, standards, regulations, suppliers, manufacturers and cyber-security experts. **A4 Cyber-security Experts:** They integrate security aspects in software applications and complex systems. They protect our system networks, devices and users' data from unauthorised access. **A5 Supplier and Manufacturer:** In recent Industry evolution from Industry 1.0 to Industry 4.0, and to Industry 5.0, collaboration with suppliers and manufacturers becomes vital. Further mandatory elements are trustworthiness and adequate quality for all stakeholders involved. **A6 Standards and Regulations:** General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) plays a paramount role in achieving quality standards as it brings legal aspects for better implementation and collaboration between humans/users, cyber-security experts, developers and other stakeholders.

As in Figure 5(b), HCT will impact other important sectors of the newly introduced Quality 5.0 concepts as represented by the levels around the centric HCT. As in the figure, human-centric traceability plays a role in requirements elicitation because it focuses on different sources and actors (Requirement Elicitation level of Figure 5(b)). The diversity in requirements and the integration of different knowledge ensure the development lifecycle activity focused on specific,

use, targeted quality attributes to improve the final quality (Quality 4.0 level of Figure 5(b)). Finally, the available, easy-to-read sources of evidence collected during the requirement traceability can certainly increase the final product's overall trustworthiness (Trustworthiness level of Figure 5(b)).

6 Expected Results and conclusions

Future work involves exploring and integrating artificial intelligence (AI) and digital twins to mitigate cyber-security threats. The expected results focus on providing techniques, facilities and platforms to let people understand cyber-security. Moreover, guide their behaviors about privacy risk and let them control and manage the desired quality level while going into Quality 5.0. The recent pandemic has been a milestone for the progress of spatial computing, metaverse and digitalization. The people-first and human-centric approach to cybersecurity and privacy is intended to convert users and employees into proactive warriors. Human-centricity will always be vital and considered the backbone to discover new horizons to yield benefits from Metaverse, Industry 5.0, while providing models or quality standards to implement Quality 5.0.

References

1. Azure identity & access security best practices — Microsoft Learn. In Azure Security Fundamentals Documentations. Andrade (2022)
2. A Comprehensive Study of the IoT Cybersecurity in Smart Cities. IEEE Access. Andrade, R. O., Yoo, S. G., Tello-Oquendo, L., & Ortiz-Garces, I. (2020).
3. A Quality 4.0 Model for architecting industry 4.0 systems. Advanced Engineering Informatics, 54. Antonino, P. O., Capilla, R., Pelliccione, P., Schnicke, F., Espen, D., Kuhn, T., & Schmid, K. (2022).
4. Quality 4.0 and its impact on organizational performance: an integrative viewpoint. TQM Journal, 34(6), 2069–2084. Antony, J., Sony, M., Furterer, S., McDermott, O., & Pepper, M. (2022).
5. Quality 4-0 — ASQ. American Society for Quality. ASQ. (2023).
6. Industry 5.0 Beyond Technology: An Analysis Through the Lens of Business and Operations Management Literature. Organizacija, 55(4), 305–321. Borchardt, M., Pereira, G. M., Milan, G. S., Scavarda, A. R., Nogueira, E. O., & Poltosi, L. C. (2022).
7. Cybersecurity for Industrial Internet of Things: Architecture, Models and Lessons Learned. IEEE Access, 10, Bravos, G., Cabrera, A. J., Correa, C., Danilovic, D., Evangelidou, N., Ezov, G., Gajica, Z., Jakovetic, D., Kallipolitis, L., Lukic, M., Mascolo, J., Maserà, D., Mazo, R., Mezei, I., Miaoudakis, A., Milosevic, N., Oliff, W., Robin, J., Smyrlis, M., . . . Vukobratovic, D. (2022).
8. Industry 5.0 - Towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry. Breque, & Nul, D. (2021).
9. A novel Security-by-Design methodology: modeling and assessing security with a quantitative approach. Casola, V., & Benedictis, A. De. (2020).
10. Report on the 2nd Workshop on Human Centric Software Engineering & Cyber Security. ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes, 47(2), 12–14. Chhetri, M. B., Liu, X., Grobler, M., Hoang, T., Renaud, K., & McIntosh, J. (2022).

11. Cybersecurity in the context of industry 4.0: A structured classification of critical assets and business impacts. *Computers in Industry*, 114, 103165. Corallo, A., Lazoi, M., & Lezzi, M. (2020).
12. Industry 5.0: The Prelude to the Sixth Industrial Revolution. *Applied System Innovation 2021*, Vol. 4, Page 45, 4(3), 45. Di Nardo, M., & Yu, H. (2021).
13. Research challenges of industry 4.0 for quality management. *Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing*, 245, 121–137. Foidl, H., & Felderer, M. (2016).
14. Industry 5.0: improving humanization and sustainability of Industry 4.0. *Scientometrics*, 127(6), 3117–3144. Grabowska, S., Saniuk, S., & Gajdzik, B. (2022).
15. From Industry 4.0 to Construction 5.0: Exploring the Path towards Human & Robot Collaboration in Construction. *Systems 2023*, Vol. 11, Page 152, 11(3), 152. Hosseinian-Far, A., Varga, L., Daneshkhah, A., & Marinelli, M. (2023).
16. The Industry 5.0 framework: viability-based integration of the resilience, sustainability, and human-centricity perspectives. *International Journal of Production Research*. Ivanov, D. (2022).
17. Industry 5.0: Prospect and retrospect. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 65, 279–295. Leng, J., Sha, W., Wang, B., Zheng, P., Zhuang, C., Liu, Q., Wuest, T., Mourtzis, D., & Wang, L. (2022).
18. Industry 5.0: A survey on enabling technologies and potential applications. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 26, 100257. Maddikunta, P. K. R., Pham, Q. V., B, P., Deepa, N., Dev, K., Gadekallu, T. R., Ruby, R., & Liyanage, M. (2022).
19. The Precipitative Effects of Pandemic on Open Innovation of SMEs: A Scientometrics and Systematic Review of Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(3), 152. Madhavan, M., Wangtueai, S., Sharafuddin, M. A., & Chaichana, T. (2022).
20. An Exploratory Bibliometric Analysis of the Birth and Emergence of Industry 5.0. *Applied System Innovation 2021*, Vol. 4, Page 87, 4(4), 87. Madsen, D. Ø., & Berg, T. (2021).
21. The emergence of Industry 5.0: a bibliometric analysis. *International Conference on Quality and Engineering Management (ICQEM 2022)*At: Braga, Portugal. Martins, Y. S., Domingues, P., Poltronieri, C. F., & Leite, L. R. (2022).
22. Industry 5.0—A Human-Centric Solution. *Sustainability 2019*, Vol. 11, Page 4371, 11(16), 4371. Nahavandi, S. (2019).
23. Quality 4.0 Maturity Assessment in Light of the Current Situation in the Czech Republic. *Sustainability 2022*, Vol. 14, Page 7519, 14(12), 7519. Nenadál, J., Vykydal, D., Halfarová, P., & Tylečková, E. (2022).
24. Essential ingredients for the implementation of Quality 4.0: A narrative review of literature and future directions for research. *TQM Journal*, 32(4), 779–793. Sony, M., Antony, J., & Douglas, J. A. (2020).
25. Motivations, barriers and readiness factors for Quality 4.0 implementation: an exploratory study. *TQM Journal*, 33(6), 1502–1515. Sony, M., Antony, J., Douglas, J. A., & McDermott, O. (2021).
26. Human-Centric Cybersecurity: How to make ‘People Matter.’ *Titan*. (2023).
27. Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0—Inception, conception and perception. *J. of Manufacturing Systems*, 61, 530–535. Xu, X., Lu, Y., Vogel-Heuser, B., & Wang, L. (2021).
28. Quality 4.0—the challenging future of quality engineering. *Quality Engineering*, 32(4), 614–626. Zonnenshain, A., & Kenett, R. S. (2020).
29. Free e-Theses portal – Bahria University. Bahria University. Waheed, T. (2020).

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Process

